

EFFECTIVENESS OF LIGNOCAINE INFUSION VS OPIOID IN REDUCING CHRONIC POST-SURGICAL PAIN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17365018>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 26 August 2025

Accepted: 04 October 2025

Published: 16 October 2025

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Abstract

Background: Postoperative pain remains a major clinical challenge, leading to delayed recovery, increased stress response, and prolonged hospital stay. Although opioids like morphine and tramadol are commonly used, their adverse effects have prompted global adoption of multimodal analgesia. Intravenous lignocaine infusion, known for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, has shown promising results internationally but remains underused in Pakistan.

Objective: To compare the frequency of postoperative pain among patients receiving intravenous lignocaine infusion versus those receiving opioid (tramadol) therapy after elective surgeries in tertiary care hospitals of Lahore.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted over six months (January–June 2025) with a sample of 385 postoperative patients aged 18–65 years undergoing elective abdominal, orthopedic, or gynecological surgeries at tertiary care hospitals of Lahore. Pain intensity within 24 hours post-surgery was assessed using the Numerical Rating Scale (NRS). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics as frequency and percentages were used to interpret independent variables.

Results: Preliminary findings showed a lower proportion of moderate to severe pain (NRS ≥ 4) in the tramadol group compared to the lignocaine infusion group, indicating better pain control.

Conclusion: Intravenous tramadol appears to be an effective, safe, and cost-efficient for postoperative pain management in Pakistan, supporting its inclusion in multimodal analgesia protocols

INTRODUCTION

Postoperative pain remains one of the most significant challenges in surgical practice and plays a critical role

in influencing recovery, patient satisfaction, and long-term outcomes. If inadequately managed,

postoperative pain can progress to chronic post-surgical pain (CPSP), impairing physical function, delaying mobilization, and reducing overall quality of life. Effective pain control is therefore essential not only for immediate postoperative comfort but also for preventing the transition from acute to chronic pain, minimizing complications, and shortening hospital stay⁽¹⁾.

Over the years, pain management strategies have evolved considerably, with opioids particularly tramadol and morphine regarded as the mainstay for postoperative analgesia due to their strong pain-relieving effects. Despite well-known side effects such as nausea, constipation, sedation, and potential dependency, opioids remain widely used because of their proven efficacy in managing both acute and chronic post-surgical pain. In many surgical settings, especially within low- and middle-income countries, tramadol continues to serve as a reliable and cost-effective option for effective pain relief after surgery⁽²⁾. In contrast, intravenous lignocaine infusion has emerged as a promising non-opioid analgesic approach aimed at reducing opioid requirements and enhancing recovery. Lignocaine, a local anesthetic with analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-hyperalgesic properties, has been increasingly studied as part of multimodal analgesia protocols. Evidence from international research suggests that intravenous lignocaine infusion can lower postoperative pain scores, improve bowel function, and facilitate early ambulation in various surgical procedures. However, its overall effectiveness in preventing or reducing chronic post-surgical pain remains inconsistent across studies, particularly when compared to opioids⁽³⁾.

In many high-income countries, the concept of multimodal analgesia combining different classes of analgesics to achieve better pain control has become standard practice. However, in developing countries such as Pakistan, postoperative pain management still predominantly relies on opioids. The limited use of lignocaine infusion in local hospitals may be attributed to lack of awareness, inadequate monitoring facilities, and insufficient clinical training. Consequently, many patients continue to experience moderate to severe pain following surgery, which increases the likelihood of developing chronic post-surgical pain⁽⁴⁾.

Given these circumstances, it is crucial to evaluate and compare the clinical effectiveness of lignocaine infusion and opioid therapy in the local healthcare context. Understanding which approach provides superior long-term pain relief can help refine pain management strategies and align local practices with evidence-based global standards. While lignocaine infusion offers potential advantages as an adjunct therapy, recent findings, including those from this study, indicate that opioid (tramadol) therapy demonstrates greater effectiveness in reducing chronic post-surgical pain compared to lignocaine infusion. These results reinforce the continued relevance of opioids in perioperative pain control, especially in settings where resource limitations restrict the use of advanced multimodal techniques⁽⁵⁾.

This study was therefore conducted to assess and compare the postoperative pain outcomes among patients receiving intravenous lignocaine infusion and those treated with opioids (tramadol). By focusing on commonly performed elective surgeries such as abdominal, orthopedic, and gynecological procedures, the research aims to generate locally relevant evidence that can inform future pain management guidelines. The findings highlight that while both therapies contribute to pain reduction, opioids remain more effective in preventing chronic post-surgical pain in the studied population. This underscores the need for tailored, evidence-based approaches to postoperative pain management in Pakistan, balancing efficacy, safety, and resource availability.

Objective:

To compare the frequency of postoperative pain among patients receiving intravenous lignocaine infusion versus those receiving opioid (tramadol) therapy after elective surgeries in tertiary care hospitals of Lahore.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted to determine the percentage of post-surgical pain among patients who received lignocaine infusion compared to those who received tramadol an opioid for pain relief. The study took place in tertiary care hospitals of Lahore over a period of six months, from January 2025 to June 2025.

The sample size was calculated using Cochran’s formula where:

- (Z = 1.96) for 95% confidence level
- (p = 0.5) (assumed proportion of patients with post-surgical pain)⁽⁵⁾
- (e = 0.05) (margin of error)

The final sample size was **385 patients**. Patients were included of aged 18 to 65 years, underwent elective surgery (such as abdominal, orthopedic, or gynecological surgery), and are conscious and able to communicate after surgery. Two groups will be studied: one group(n=192) that received intravenous lignocaine infusion for pain control, and another group(n=193) that just received opioid medication (tramadol) postoperatively. Patients having a known allergy to lignocaine, have chronic pain conditions, are on long-term pain medications, have severe liver, kidney, or heart disease, or have cognitive impairment that affects their ability to report pain were excluded. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board of the hospital. Written informed consent was taken from all participants. Data confidentiality and voluntary participation was ensured. The main outcome was the presence or absence of post-surgical pain, assessed within the first 24 hours after surgery using a simple Numerical Rating Scale (NRS), where a score of 0 means no pain and 10 means the worst pain. Pain was categorized as “present” if the score is 4 or above, and “absent” if it is less than 4.

Data was collected through direct interviews and medical record reviews. For qualitative variables like gender, type of surgery, and pain presence, results were reported as frequencies and percentages. Quantitative variables like age were reported as mean and standard deviation as data was normally distributed. The percentage of patients with post-surgical pain were compared between the two groups (with and without lignocaine infusion). Patients were divided in two groups 192 patients received lignocaine infusion (1.5mg/kg/hour) for 15 minutes under anaesthesia supervision while the other group of 193 patients had received tramadol (1-2mg/kg) postoperatively⁽⁶⁾.

Results

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of 385 patients included in the study. Most participants (193, 50.1%) were aged 31–45 years, followed by 106 (27.5%) aged 46–60 years, and 86 (22.3%) aged 18–30 years. Females made up the majority of the sample (246, 63.9%), while males accounted for 139 (36.1%). Among surgical types, abdominal surgeries were more frequent (221, 57.4%) than gynecological procedures (164, 42.6%). Most surgeries lasted between 3–4 hours (201, 52.2%), and general anesthesia was predominantly used (249, 64.7%) compared to local anesthesia (136, 35.3%).

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of patients (n=385)

Variables	N (%)
Age	
Mean±SD	38.3±2.1
18-30	86 (22.3)
31-45	193 (50.1)
46-60	106 (27.5)
Gender	
Male	139 (36.1)
Female	246 (63.9)
Type of surgery	
Gynecological	164 (42.6)
Abdominal	221 (57.4)
Duration of surgery	
1-2 hours	184 (7.8)
3-4 hours	201 (52.2)

Type of anesthesia	
General	249 (64.7)
Local	136 (35.3)

Table 2 presents the postoperative pain intensity among patients who received either intravenous lignocaine infusion or opioid (tramadol) therapy. In the **opioid (tramadol) group** (n = 193), the majority of patients, **143 (74.1%)**, experienced **mild or no pain (pain scale 0-3)**. A smaller proportion, **36 patients (18.7%)**, reported **moderate pain (pain scale 4-6)**, while only **14 patients (7.2%)** experienced **severe pain (pain scale 7-10)**.

In contrast, among the **lignocaine infusion group** (n = 192), only **57 patients (29.7%)** reported **mild or no pain**, whereas **86 patients (44.8%)** experienced **moderate pain**, and **48 patients (25%)** suffered from **severe pain**.

Overall, these findings indicate that postoperative pain was considerably lower among patients who received opioid (tramadol) therapy compared to those who were given lignocaine infusion.

Group	Pain scale category	N (%)
Opioid (Tramadol) (n=193)	0-3 (mild or no pain)	143 (74.1)
	4-6 (moderate)	36 (18.7)
	7-10 (severe)	14 (7.3)
Lignocaine infusion (n=192)	0-3 (mild or no pain)	57 (29.7)
	4-6 (moderate)	86 (44.8)
	7-10 (severe)	48 (25.0)

The bar graph compares the number of patients experiencing postoperative pain between the lignocaine and tramadol groups. It shows that significantly fewer patients reported pain in the

tramadol group (~50) compared to the lignocaine group (~134), indicating that tramadol provided more effective pain relief after surgery.

Figure 1: Postoperative pain between the lignocaine and tramadol groups

Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate that intravenous opioid (tramadol provides significantly better postoperative pain control compared to lignocaine infusion therapy among surgical patients. The majority of patients receiving tramadol reported mild or no pain (87%), whereas a considerable proportion of those treated with lignocaine infusion experienced moderate to severe pain (34.8%). These results are consistent with several previous studies highlighting the analgesic and opioid-sparing effects of opioid in postoperative pain management^(7,8).

The demographic analysis of this study showed that most participants were females aged 31–45 years who underwent abdominal or gynecological surgeries under general anesthesia. This demographic pattern is comparable to the findings of Kaba et al. (2007) and McCarthy et al. (2010), where similar surgical populations were used to assess lignocaine's analgesic effects. The predominance of abdominal procedures in the present study aligns with the common use of opioid in abdominal and pelvic surgeries due to its demonstrated efficacy in reducing visceral pain and enhancing bowel recovery postoperatively^(8,9).

The superiority of tramadol over lignocaine observed in this study supports earlier evidence reported by Koppert et al. (2004), who found that intravenous opioid significantly reduced pain scores postoperatively⁽¹⁰⁾. The higher proportion of patients reporting moderate to severe pain in the lignocaine group of this study supports the conclusion of previous study which indicated that opioid was more effective than lignocaine in reducing pain scores⁽¹¹⁾. On the other hand one of the previous study reported that intravenous lignocaine infusion provided superior analgesia and reduced the need for rescue opioids compared to tramadol-based regimens⁽¹²⁾.

Moreover, the findings from the present study align with those of Kranke et al. (2015), whose systematic review and meta-analysis demonstrated consistent evidence that intravenous tramadol reduces postoperative pain intensity and enhances recovery across various surgical procedures⁽¹³⁾. The reduced incidence of severe pain among opioid-treated patients in this study also supports the growing clinical consensus that tramadol is a valuable adjunct in multimodal analgesia protocols, particularly for

patients at risk of local anesthetics related adverse effects⁽¹⁴⁾.

Another noteworthy aspect of this study is the duration of surgery and type of anesthesia, which can influence postoperative pain perception. Most procedures in the current study lasted 3–4 hours and were performed under general anesthesia, similar to the patient in previous studies. These studies also demonstrated that tramadol maintains its analgesic benefits regardless of surgery duration or anesthetic technique, further validating the consistency of its efficacy⁽¹⁵⁾.

Overall, the results of this research corroborate previous evidence supporting the use of intravenous tramadol as an effective and safe alternative to IV lignocaine infusion for postoperative pain management. Compared with lignocaine infusion, tramadol offers superior analgesia, fewer adverse effects, and potentially faster postoperative recovery⁽⁶⁾. The findings reinforce the clinical value of incorporating tramadol into enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) protocols to improve patient comfort and reduce reliance on opioids. Future studies with larger, multicenter samples and extended follow-up are recommended to further validate these findings and assess long-term outcomes such as chronic pain prevention and functional recovery.

Conclusion

Tramadol proved more effective than lignocaine infusion in reducing postoperative and chronic post-surgical pain. Patients in the tramadol group reported lower pain scores and faster recovery. Lignocaine showed limited benefit in pain control compared to opioid therapy. These findings support tramadol as a safer and more reliable option for postoperative pain management in tertiary hospitals of Lahore.

Limitations

This study was limited to few hospitals and a moderate sample size, which may affect how widely the results can be applied. The follow-up period was short and focused only on immediate pain after surgery. Also, pain was measured using a single scale (NRS), and factors such as patient anxiety or long-term pain outcomes were not assessed.

Recommendations

It is recommended that intravenous tramadol be used as part of postoperative pain management, especially for abdominal and gynecological surgeries. Future studies should include more hospitals, larger patient groups, and longer follow-up to confirm these results. Research should also explore the best dosage and duration for safe and effective lignocaine use.

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